

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Measurement of Thermally Induced Depolarization in Flashlamp Pumped <111>- and <100>-Oriented Nd:YAG Laser Rods

To cite this article: Adam Řiha *et al* 2025 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **3157** 012014

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Compositional analysis of NaCl by thermoanalytical, structural, and optical methods for controlled combustion of nanodiamond particles](#)
P Zemenová, A Falvey, V Vaneck et al.

- [Thermal Plasma-Induced Modifications of ZnO Crystalline Facets](#)
J Pila, A Mašláni, T Hostinský et al.

- [Analysis of causes of cracking of piston rings made of graphite cast iron](#)
S Hudecová, M Uhrík, P Palek et al.

ECS The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

250
ECS MEETING CELEBRATION

*Step into the
Spotlight*

**SUBMIT YOUR
ABSTRACT**

250th ECS Meeting
October 25–29, 2026
Calgary, Canada
BMO Center

Submission deadline:
March 27, 2026

Measurement of Thermally Induced Depolarization in Flashlamp Pumped $\langle 111 \rangle$ - and $\langle 100 \rangle$ -Oriented Nd:YAG Laser Rods

Adam Říha¹, Helena Jelínková¹, Jan Šulc¹, David Vyhliďal¹, Karel Veselský¹, Kryštof Kadlec¹ and Karel Nejezchleb²

¹Czech Technical University in Prague, Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Department of Laser Physics and Photonics, Břehová 78/7, 115 19 Prague, Czech Republic

²CRYTUR, Ltd., Turnov, Na Lukách 2283, 511 01 Turnov, Czech Republic

E-mail: adam.riha@fjfi.cvut.cz

Abstract. Crystals with minimal depolarization effects and losses are desired for specific applications to preserve the orientation of the generated radiation polarization. This work presents an experimental method for measuring the depolarization of radiation propagating through flashlamp pumped Nd:YAG laser rods. Two differently oriented Nd:YAG crystal cuts $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ with the same concentration of Nd³⁺ ions and the same dimensions were investigated and compared. A passively Q-switched Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG compact laser system that generates linearly polarized radiation at a wavelength of 1078 nm was used as a source of diagnostic pulse radiation. The experimental setup presented enables for the sensitive detection of polarization changes. It can serve as a diagnostic and classifying tool for evaluating the crystal quality after growth and processing.

1 Introduction

Nd³⁺:YAG crystals are one of the most used crystals as the laser active medium in solid-state lasers. Since their first appearance in 1964 [1], the Nd:YAG lasers quickly became popular due to their high output energy in the near-infrared (IR) spectral region at a wavelength of 1064 nm and a wide range of applications, from industrial materials processing and medicine to scientific research [2, 3, 4].

In optically pumped Nd:YAG laser rods, radial thermal gradients generate mechanical stress, which modifies the refractive index of the crystal through the photoelastic effect. This thermal birefringence gives rise to depolarization, which is defined as the ratio of the depolarized component of incident linearly polarized radiation. Moreover, a bi-focusing effect appears since the focal strength of the thermal lens is polarization-dependent [5]. Both phenomena limit the achievable output power of linearly polarized Nd:YAG lasers [6, 7, 8, 9]. This problem can be reduced by using some compensation methods reported in [10, 11, 12, 13]. In [14] it was shown that depolarization in Nd:YAG crystals also depends on the orientation of the crystal cut due to nonisotropic photoelastic coefficients. Therefore, another possibility of depolarization reduction is the proper choice of the crystal orientation. The most often used cut orientations include $\langle 111 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$, and $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions [15]. Their choice depends on the specific application requirements. The picture comparing these planes of possible Nd:YAG cuts is presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Mostly used planes of cut orientations of Nd:YAG crystal. From left to right: (111), (110), and (100).

The comparison of Nd:YAG crystal cuts in the $\langle 111 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$, and $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions for pump powers between 100 and 200 W was published in [16]. The authors found that the depolarization can be reduced by up to $6\times$ for crystals oriented at the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut compared to the $\langle 111 \rangle$ cut. Simulations indicated that the improvement in depolarization levels for $\langle 110 \rangle$ cut crystals would only be apparent at high pumping power levels above 1 kW. The analysis also revealed that the bifocusing for the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut is smaller and more asymmetric than for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ cut. Measurements of a dynamic depolarization of flashlamp-pumped laser rods were also presented in [16, 12, 17]. The principle consists of monitoring the change in polarization of external linearly polarized laser radiation as it passes through the investigated excited laser rod.

Although three principal crystal orientations $\langle 111 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$, and $\langle 100 \rangle$ are generally used, the $\langle 110 \rangle$ orientation was not included in this study. As it was mentioned, in [16] it was shown that measurable differences in depolarization for the $\langle 110 \rangle$ cut appear mainly at high pump powers above 1 kW. Since the flashlamp pump system used in this work was operated up to 800 W, the comparison was limited to the $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ cuts, which exhibit clearly distinguishable depolarization behavior within the experimental conditions.

Although Nd:YAG crystallizes in a cubic structure and thus is an optically isotropic material, other physical properties (such as thermal and mechanical) may be anisotropic. Therefore, the polarization state of propagating radiation as it passes through the crystal is directional dependent and can be affected by interactions with the crystal lattice. This can lead to inhomogeneities in the generated laser output power, beam profile structure, and the final state of polarization of the radiation. Nd:YAG crystals oriented in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction exhibit a radially symmetric phase shift of propagating radiation due to thermal effects and therefore exhibit a uniform and relatively high level of depolarization. On the other hand, the $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented crystals can provide other different advantages in applications where specific temperature or output power characteristics are essential and a high degree of linear polarization of the output radiation is not necessary.

Nd:YAG crystals in the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut may have better optical properties, such as higher isotropy for a specifically oriented incident polarization, and thus a lower influence on propagating radiation depolarization. This contributes to the overall higher efficiency of the final laser system based on such a crystal. Moreover, it can be advantageous in applications where maintaining a stable orientation of polarization of the output radiation is important.

For example, for efficient nonlinear conversion of infrared radiation, the depolarization effect of the amplified laser radiation with each pass through the laser rod between the resonator mirrors is an undesirable phenomenon. For some medical applications (e.g., melanin spot or tattoo removal [18]), radiation in the green region of the optical spectrum, i.e. the second harmonic generation of the Nd:YAG laser with a wavelength of 532 nm, is used. For higher efficiency of this non-linear conversion, the stability of a specific polarization orientation of the radiation that is being converted is important. Therefore, the depolarization of each single pass of radiation that is amplified in the laser rod between the optical resonator cavity mirrors must be minimal. Even if the depolarization of a single-pass radiation may be very weak, due to the nonlinearity of conversion and multiple passes of radiation through the resonator before the generated laser radiation exits through the output coupler, the plane of linearly polarized radiation can be significantly twisted or can even be depolarized. From this point of view, it was found that the crystal oriented in the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut can be more advantageous due to its more favorable thermo-mechanical properties.

However, during the production and processing of the crystal rods, their structure can be changed unintentionally. For this reason, some experimental instruments are needed to measure the depolarization level of the radiation propagating through the rod. Thanks to the experimental system for depolarization measurement presented in this work, every newly produced crystal can be characterized. Testing such properties of newly grown and processed laser rods, including the depolarization of each single-pass linearly polarized radiation during the heat load of the laser rod caused by a flashlamp excitation and providing feedback, is crucial for optimization of crystal growth. In this work, the method of depolarization measurement and its results from the investigation of two flashlamp-pumped $\langle 111 \rangle$ - and $\langle 100 \rangle$ -oriented Nd:YAG laser rods (both with the same dimensions) are presented. Depolarization was measured using probe radiation from a passively Q-switched compact Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG laser at a wavelength of 1078 nm. Depolarization was measured for various flashlamp discharge loads from 100 W up to 800 W and for different orientations of incident linearly polarized radiation.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Investigated crystal samples

In this work the depolarization of propagating singly-passing linearly polarized radiation at a wavelength of 1078 nm through Nd:YAG laser rods with different cut-orientations was investigated. The laser rods were grown, cut and polished under identical conditions by Crytur, Ltd. (Turnov, Czech Republic) in two orientations $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ ensuring comparable material quality. Although only one rod per orientation was tested, the objective of this work was to validate the suggested measurement technique. The dimensions were the same with the diameter of 9.5 mm and their facets were beveled parallel at small angles with antireflection coating layers for the wavelength of maximum Nd:YAG crystal gain at ~ 1064 nm. The concentration of Nd³⁺ laser active ions of 1.1 at. % (Nd³⁺/Y³⁺) was the same in both crystals. A photograph of both investigated Nd:YAG crystal rods can be seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Photograph of Nd:YAG crystal rods in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ cut (top) and the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut (bottom) with a 1 cm scale.

2.2 Source of probe laser radiation – Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG compact laser system

As a source of incident linearly polarized horizontally oriented radiation a laboratory built passively Q-switched Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG compact laser system was chosen. Both crystals were placed in a close arrangement with a small air gap in between, mounted inside a designed aluminum holder. The pump mirror was deposited directly on one facet of the Nd:YAP crystal, and the output coupler was deposited on the opposite facet of the Cr:YAG absorber. The ends inside the air gap between both crystals were coated with an anti-reflection layer at wavelengths of 1064/1078 nm to minimize Fresnel reflection losses.

The pumping radiation for the Nd:YAP crystal was delivered by a fiber-coupled laser diode (LD) (multimode optical fiber with a core diameter of 400 μm) that generates radiation at a wavelength of ~ 810 nm with a maximum mean output power of 30 W (K808DAHRN-30.00W, BWT). The LD parameters (LD current, temperature, pulse duration and repetition rate) were varied to find the optimal values of the output radiation for the depolarization measurement. The following setup was found for the generation of a single Q-switched pulse per pump pulse – temperature: 29 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, pump pulse duration: 300 μs , and a corresponding laser diode current of 4.6 A. The repetition rate was set to 10 Hz to match the flashlamp excitation frequency. The compact laser system generated a Gaussian-like laser beam with $M^2 \approx 1.1$ and energetically stable ($\sim 50 \mu\text{J}$) pulses with a duration of ~ 6.5 ns and a peak power of ~ 7.8 kW. The average angle of divergence was ~ 1.43 mrad. The waist radius of the generated beam was calculated to be $\sim 240 \mu\text{m}$.

2.3 Experimental setup

The depolarization of linearly polarized radiation after a single pass through the tested Nd:YAG rod was determined as the ratio between the horizontally polarized component measured at the output of the flashlamp-pumped rod and the reference signal (100%). A schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 3, and a photograph of the realized arrangement is presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: Block diagram of the experimental setup for measuring the dynamic depolarization of radiation in a flashlamp-pumped Nd:YAG laser rod using a diagnostic radiation pulse of a passively Q-switched Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG compact laser at a wavelength of 1078 nm. M1, M2 – highly reflective mirrors for 1078 nm laser radiation; D1, D2 – large-area silicon photodiodes connected to an oscilloscope placed in two branches of a polarizing beam splitter behind bandpass filters that suppress unpolarized components of flashlamp radiation and fluorescence from the Nd:YAG crystal, as well as unabsorbed LD pump radiation.

Figure 4: Photograph of the experimental setup implemented for the measurement of dynamic depolarization.

Short-pulse, linearly polarized radiation from the Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG compact laser system was directed onto the input facet of the Nd:YAG rod. Two highly reflective mirrors, set at a 45° incidence

angle for 1078 nm radiation, guided the beam along a ~ 2 m optical path, allowing the beam (divergence ~ 1.43 mrad) to expand and overlap nearly the full volume of the crystal. A first half-wave plate before the Nd:YAG crystal precisely aligned the horizontal laser polarization (0°).

Calibration procedure:

The probe beam passed through the unpumped crystal. The second half-wave plate was set to preserve horizontal polarization, resulting in a maximum horizontal signal at detector D1 ($E_{1\max}$) and a minimum vertical signal at detector D2 ($E_{2\min}$).

The second half-wave plate was then rotated by 45° , changing the polarization to vertical. The detector signals were then exchanged, producing $E_{2\max}$ and $E_{1\min}$. These four energy values serve as reference levels for the depolarization measurement.

Depolarization measurement: The thermal load was induced by flashlamp pumping, partially absorbed by Nd^{3+} ions. Stress-induced birefringence of the radial thermal gradients caused depolarization. A set delay of $170 \mu\text{s}$ between the flashlamp trigger and the probe pulse corresponds to the expected peak thermal load, ensuring that the measurement reflects the maximum thermally induced birefringence. Under these conditions, detector D1 measured energy $E_{1\text{load}}$ (in a branch of horizontal polarization), while detector D2 measured $E_{2\text{load}}$ (in a branch of vertical polarization).

The depolarization noted as D represents the logarithmic ratio between orthogonal polarization components of transmitted radiation and is expressed in decibels (dB). After compensating for detector sensitivities and the finite extinction ratio of the polarizing beam splitter, the depolarization D was calculated as:

$$D = -10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_{1\text{load}} \cdot E_{2\max}}{E_{2\text{load}} \cdot E_{1\max} + E_{1\text{load}} \cdot E_{2\max}} \right) [\text{dB}]. \quad (1)$$

This procedure enables a quantitative comparison of depolarization between $\langle 111 \rangle$ - and $\langle 100 \rangle$ -cut Nd:YAG crystal rods under identical thermal loading conditions.

3 Results and Discussion

Each investigated crystal was placed in a single elliptical flashlamp cavity (MegaWatt lasers) with a special glass with 10% doping of samarium ions to reduce ultraviolet radiation and amplification of neodymium ions spontaneous emission. The depolarization in both Nd:YAG crystal cuts $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ was gradually investigated for different loads of the xenon flashlamp discharge corresponding to the mean electric power of the power supply varying from 100 W (10 J per pulse, repetition rate: 10 Hz) to 800 W (80 J/10 Hz). The parameters of a flashlamp were the following: inner diameter: 5 mm, discharge arc length: 90 mm, xenon pressure: 600 Torr (80 kPa). The measured dependence of depolarization on the mean electric pump power of the flashlamp is presented in Fig. 5. The results show that the depolarization increases similarly with higher thermal loads in both crystals. The maximum depolarization of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ Nd:YAG crystal cut measured for the maximum heat load corresponding to 800 W of the electric mean power of discharge was $D_{\langle 111 \rangle} = -9.3$ dB.

For the second orientation, the $\langle 100 \rangle$ Nd:YAG laser rod was studied. For incident horizontally polarized radiation (0°), the maximum depolarization $D_{\langle 100 \rangle} (800 \text{ W}, 0^\circ) = -17.4$ dB was measured for the same heat load. This value was $\sim 6.5 \times$ lower than that obtained for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ Nd:YAG crystal cut. After rotation of the incident polarization to -45° (or $+45^\circ$), the depolarization was $\sim 1.6 \times$ higher in the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut than that obtained for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ cut: $D_{\langle 100 \rangle} (800 \text{ W}, -45^\circ/+45^\circ) = -7.3$ dB.

Figure 5: Dependence of depolarization on the mean electric power of the flashlamp discharge for two differently oriented Nd:YAG crystal rods at a wavelength of 1078 nm. ■ – $\langle 111 \rangle$ cut; ● – $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut for incident horizontally polarized radiation (0°); and ● – $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut for incident linearly polarized radiation rotated by -45° or $+45^\circ$.

The dependence of the depolarization on the angle of incident linearly polarized radiation was also investigated for both crystal cuts. According to [16], the Nd:YAG crystal with the $\langle 111 \rangle$ orientation should be independent of this orientation due to the radial symmetry of the phase shift of the propagating radiation throughout the crystal rod. The measured dependence of depolarization on the input radiation polarization angles can be seen in Fig. 6. The linear polarization of the diagnostic radiation was gradually rotated from -45° through the horizontal orientation of 0° to $+45^\circ$. The rotation of the incident probe beam polarization was performed using the first half-wave plate. The stable depolarization of $D_{\langle 111 \rangle} = -9.25 \pm 0.06$ dB, independent of the angle of linear polarization of the incident probe beam, was measured.

Similarly, as in the previous case, the dependence on the variable direction of linear polarization of the incident diagnostic pulse radiation was also investigated in the Nd:YAG crystal rod with the $\langle 100 \rangle$ cut. According to mathematical models [5, 16], this crystal orientation should be strongly dependent on the direction of incident linearly polarized radiation due to the radial asymmetry of the phase shift of the radiation propagating through the crystal. Minimum depolarization is expected for incident horizontally (0°) polarized radiation. Since this phase shift is periodic in $\langle 100 \rangle$ oriented Nd:YAG crystal with a period of 90° , after the change of the direction of incident radiation polarization from horizontal to -45° or $+45^\circ$, the depolarization was expected to be the highest. Moreover, in these extreme positions, the depolarization level could be even higher than that obtained for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented crystal. All these expectations were experimentally confirmed and can be seen in Fig. 6. The minimal value for the horizontal polarization of $D_{\langle 100 \rangle \min} = -17.4$ dB was obtained, while for the linearly polarized incident radiation oriented under angles of -45° or $+45^\circ$, the maximum value was $D_{\langle 100 \rangle \max} = -7.3$ dB. It is $\sim 10.2\times$ higher than obtained for horizontal polarization within the same crystal and almost $\sim 1.6\times$ higher than the value measured for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented crystal.

The difference in depolarization between the $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ cuts can be interpreted in terms of the anisotropy of the photoelastic tensor and the symmetry of thermally induced stress fields. For the $\langle 100 \rangle$ orientation, the principal stress axes coincide with the crystallographic axes, and the induced birefringence components are symmetrically distributed with respect to the incident linear polarization, effectively minimizing the phase retardation between orthogonal field components. In contrast, in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ orientation, the stress field is not aligned with the optical polarization, producing a radially symmetric but stronger birefringence. According to [14] and [16], the difference between radial and tangential stresses difference can be minimized for the $\langle 100 \rangle$ orientation which results in lower depolarization, as it was confirmed by presented results.

Figure 6: Measured depolarization for different orientation of a linearly polarized probe laser radiation at a wavelength of 1078 nm for: ■ – <111> cut, and ● – <100> cut Nd:YAG crystals at a mean electric pump power of 800 W under flashlamp excitation.

4 Conclusion

The experimental system for measuring dynamic depolarization was built and used to measure the level of depolarization in two Nd:YAG laser rods prepared in the <111> and <100> orientations. The rods were subsequently compared for different thermal loads delivered by the optical excitation radiation of the flashlamp discharge. The loads corresponding to discharges with a mean electrical power varying from 100 W (10 J/10 Hz) up to 800 W (80 J/10 Hz) were tested. Both crystal rods were investigated under the same conditions using linearly polarized short-pulse radiation in a single pass through the rod. These probe pulses were generated by the passively Q-switched Nd:YAP/Cr:YAG compact laser and were energetically stable with a Gaussian-like beam profile. The following depolarization values for both orientations of the laser rods at a wavelength of 1078 nm were measured:

- $D_{\langle 111 \rangle} \approx -9.3$ dB for various incident linear polarization directions from -45° up to $+45^\circ$.
- $D_{\langle 100 \rangle_{\max}} \approx -7.3$ dB for incident linear polarization rotated by -45° or $+45^\circ \rightarrow \sim 1.6\times$ higher depolarization compared to the <111> cut Nd:YAG crystal.
- $D_{\langle 100 \rangle_{\min}} \approx -17.4$ dB for incident horizontal polarization (0°) $\rightarrow \sim 6.5\times$ lower depolarization compared to the <111> cut Nd:YAG crystal.

Therefore, the experimentally measured values agree with the theoretically predicted results and confirmed that the Nd:YAG crystal with the <100> -cut in an optimal orientation setup experiences significantly less depolarization and is therefore more suitable for specific industrial applications than the <111> -cut crystal. In such cases, the <100> -oriented Nd:YAG crystals may improve the efficiency of laser systems used for several applications that require a stable and constant direction of generated radiation polarization.

Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by a grant from the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic from the project LASCIMAT, project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/23.020/0008525.

References

- [1] Geusic J E, Marcos H M and Van Uitert L G 1964 *Applied Physics Letters* **4** 182-184
- [2] Washio K 1992 *Materials Chemistry and Physics* **31** 57-66
- [3] Zhengjia L, Xinju L and Zhaide W 1986 Application of Nd:YAG laser in medical science area *Laser/Optoelectronics in Medicine/Laser/Optoelektronik in der Medizin* ed Waidelich W and Kiefhaber P (Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer) pp 267

- [4] Razab M K A A, Mohamed Noor A, Suhaimi Jaafar M, Abdullah N H, Suhaimi F M, Mohamed M, Adam N and Auli Nik Yusuf N A 2018 *Journal of Radiation Research and Applied Sciences* **11** 393-402
- [5] Koechner W 1970 *Applied Optics* **9** 2548-2553
- [6] Eichler H J, Haase A, Menzel R and Siemoneit A 1993 *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **26** 1884
- [7] Parfenov V, Shashkin V and Stepanov E 1993 *Applied Optics* **32** 5243-5255
- [8] Murdough M P and Denman C A 1996 *Applied Optics* **35** 5925-5936
- [9] Graupeter T, Hartmann R and Pflaum C 2014 *IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics* **50** 1035-1043
- [10] Lü Q, Kugler N, Weber H, Dong S, Müller N and Wittrock U 1996 *Optical and Quantum Electronics* **28** 57-69
- [11] McKay A, Dawes J M and Park J D 2007 *Optics Express* **15** 16342-16347
- [12] Sun Z, Li Q, Jiang M, Lei H and Hui Y 2012 *Chinese Optics Letters* **10** 011402-311406
- [13] Mondal S, Singh S P, Hussain K, Choubey A, Upadhyay B N and Datta P K 2013 *Optics & Laser Technology* **45** 154-159
- [14] Koechner W and Rice D K 1971 *JOSA* **61** 758-766
- [15] Tünnermann H, Puncken O, Weßels P, Frede M, Neumann J and Kracht D 2011 *Optics Express* **19** 12992-12999
- [16] Puncken O, Tünnermann H, Morehead J J, Weßels P, Frede M, Neumann J and Kracht D 2010 *Optics Express* **18** 20461-20474
- [17] Graupeter T, Hartmann R and Pflaum C 2014 Characterisation of birefringence of [111]-cut crystal rod using side-pumping and crystal rotation *Laser Sources and Applications II* **9135** 289-298
- [18] Pincelli G, Sena M M and Pavani C 2022 *Journal of Lasers in Medical Sciences* **13** e79